

Rigidized 3-aminocoumarins as fluorescent pH probes for strongly acidic environments

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Abstract

Coumarins remain one of the most important group of fluorescent bio-probes, thanks to their high quantum yields, excellent photostability, efficient cell permeation and low (cyto)toxicity. Herein, we introduce new 3-aminocoumarin turn-on pH probes for strongly acidic conditions, capable of significantly improved yeast vacuolar lumen staining compared to the commercial CMAC derivatives. We present the details of the on-off switching mechanism revealed by the TD-DFT and *ab initio* calculations complemented by a Franck-Condon analysis of the probes' emission profiles.

Keywords: Fluorescence, Coumarin, Turn-on pH probes, Highly acidic conditions, Yeast vacuolar lumen staining

1. Introduction

Determination of pH is of great importance in many applications including sensing, food production, clinical diagnostics and others [1–3]. pH sensing methods based on use of fluorescence probes are an appealing option thanks to their high sensitivity, speed, non-invasiveness and excellent spatial/temporal resolution [4–9]. While many fluorescence pH probes have been developed [5,10–14], most are designed for studies in neutral (pH=7-8) [15–17] and slightly acidic (pH=4-6) [18–22] media, particularly for real-time *in-situ* visualization of molecular processes/structures in living cells. However, a number of microorganisms [23,24] such as *Helicobacter pylori*, “acidophiles”, or pathogens [25–27] such as *Escherichia coli* and *Vibrio cholerae*, favour harsh, strongly acidic conditions (pH<4). In this work we show that a series of rigidized 3-aminocoumarins recently developed in our laboratory can serve as very effective pH probes specifically for such conditions.

In our recent report [28] we showed protonation of dimethylamino substituent in position 3 of 7-substituted 3-dimethylaminocoumarins is a promising tool for monitoring highly acidic conditions. In a related work, K.H. Ahn [29] and G. Signore [30] demonstrated that the linear and bent benzocoumarins can serve as effective ratiometric fluorescent probes for imaging intrabacterial acidity of *E. coli* as well as *endo*-lysosomal pH landscape in living cells. However, absorption maxima of the acidic forms of these coumarins fall within the cytotoxic UVA region, similarly to a new pyrene ratiometric probe introduced by J. Chao [31]. Exception is a new rhodamine-based ratiometric probe presented by X. Zeng with the absorption maximum above 500 nm [32]. While ratiometric approach is a powerful pH sensing tool, in cases where the probe has a broad emission window, it is difficult to effectively combine multiple probes in a single experiment.

The 3-dimethylaminocoumarin pH probe in our previous work [28] possessed appealing characteristics (Vis-light excitation, narrow emission window, simple off-on sensing mechanism, good fluorescence enhancement factor, rapid vacuolar staining). As a result, the probe allowed approximately 3-times faster staining of vacuoles in living *S. cerevisiae* yeast cells even at 10-times lower working concentration compared to the commercially available 7-amino-4-chloromethylcoumarin based alternatives (CellTracker™ Blue CMAC; CMAC-Ala-Pro; Ex 354 nm) [33]. In spite of the encouraging performance, its emission efficiency of the probe suffered

from twisted intramolecular charge transfer (TICT) state formation leading to low fluorescent quantum yield (~2%).

In an effort to address this limitation, in this work, we focused on rigidization of the 7-dimethylamino substituent of the 3-dimethylaminocoumarin by scaffolding a julolidyl motif, to prevent the non-emissive TICT state formation (Fig. 1). The goal was to increase the fluorescence response of the three new coumarin pH probes with varying degrees of methylation of the amino group in the position 3 of coumarin skeleton, for more efficient sensing in highly acidic environments.

Fig. 1 Molecular structure of studied coumarin fluorescent probes (arrows indicate two positions accessible for proton binding at acidic pH values).

2. Results and discussion

Figs. 2 and 3 show the effect of the pH on the PL properties of the studied coumarins. The results show that reduction in pH leads to a significant increase in yellowish-green fluorescence with chromaticity coordinates of approximately $u' = 0.12$ and $v' = 0.56$ for all three modified probes (Figs. 3 and S27). The derivatives **2** and **3** show particularly dramatic enhancement of the fluorescence intensity (quantum yield) when exposed to an acidic environment (see Table 1 and Fig. 2); with the fluorescence enhancement factor (FEF) of 9 and 12, respectively (Ex 430 nm; Figs. S23 and S24). All three derivatives thus exhibit desired turn-on fluorescent behaviour, which eliminates the false positive response commonly accompanying fluorescent turn-off probes. As demonstrated by sigmoidal fits of the fluorescence pH titration curves (Figs. S22-

Fig. 2 Evolution of the absorption (solid line) and emission (dotted line) spectra of the studied coumarin probes **2** (A) and **3** (B) during pH titration experiments. Blue vertical line indicates the corresponding excitation wavelength, whereas green vertical line indicates the position of fluorescence maximum. Letter D denotes absorption band of deprotonated (neutral) form; shortcuts JNH⁺ and ANH⁺ indicate absorption bands of protonated julolidine form and protonated amino form, respectively.

Fig. 3 The CIE 1976 (u' , v')-chromaticity diagram with marked yellowish-green fluorescence colour of studied coumarin pH probes and corresponding chromaticity coordinates u' and v' for each probe.

S24), the amino group methylation regulates not only the fluorescence enhancement factor but also the usable pH range. An addition of the dimethylamino group in the position 3 shifts the probe's pK_a value and thus the usable pH range to less acidic region (Table 1).

Table 1. Spectral characteristics and pK_a values of studied coumarin probes **1-3**.

Compound	λ_{abs} [nm]	λ_{em} [nm]	ϵ [dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹]	Φ	Bs [dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹]	pK_a
pH = 7.68 / pH = 1.90						
1	380/426	528/512	16600/11700	0.43/0.67	7100/7800	3.43
2	379/431	531/512	16800/7200	0.13/0.55	2500/4000	3.46
3	386/435	504/512	13200/17400	0.02/0.68	300/12000	4.23

λ_{abs} - UV-Vis absorption maximum, λ_{em} - emission (fluorescence) maximum, ϵ - molar absorption coefficient, Φ -

fluorescent quantum yield (accuracy: \pm 10-15 %), Bs – probe brightness ($\epsilon \times \Phi$)

As shown schematically in Fig. 1, the studied compounds contain two positions accessible for proton binding at acidic pH values. The first is the amino group in the position 3 on the coumarin skeleton and the second is the tertiary amine in the centre of the julolidine moiety. Our theoretical calculations using CAM-B3LYP/SMD/def2-TZVPP [34-36] geometry, vibrational frequency and DLPNO-CCSD(T) [37,38] /def2-TZVPP energy, revealed a shift in the protonation equilibrium between these two forms, which is also detected in the corresponding absorption spectra (Fig. 2). While the julolidine nitrogen is preferentially protonated in **1** and **2**, in compound **3** the preferred protonation site (by 10.5 kJ/mol) is the amino (dimethylamino) group (Table S1). Calculations show that the electronic transitions from the ground state (S_0) to the first singlet excited state (S_1) have high oscillator strengths for all three compounds in their protonated as well as deprotonated forms (HOMO-LUMO transitions, Fig. 4). As is schematically shown in Fig. 4, protonation of the julolidine nitrogen effectively shortens the π -conjugated system and blue-shifts the low-energy absorptions relative to the neutral compounds. In contrast, the protonation of the amino group disconnects this group from the HOMO/LUMO orbitals and results in a red shift of the vertical excitation (right column in Fig. 4). The inspection of the experimental absorption spectra reveals that both protonated forms co-exist in solution of **1** (Fig. S27) and **2** (Fig. 2A),

Fig. 4 Frontier molecular orbitals of the partially occupied S_1 state. The table below the images summarizes the vertical excitation energies calculated at various levels of theory using def2-TZVPP basis set and water as solvent. The CC2 gas phase excitation energies were corrected for solvent effects using LR CAM-B3LYP solvent shifts.

while solution of probe **3** (Fig. 2B) is dominated by the single (dimethylamino) protonated form.

As can be seen from the excitation spectrum of **2** at pH = 1.8 (Fig. S28), only excitation of its amino protonated form contributes significantly to the observed luminescence. Search for the minimum energy conical intersections (MECI) in **1** revealed that the large scale out-of-plane movements of the amino group provide a non-radiative relaxation channel connecting S_1 and S_0 states in the neutral and the julolidine protonated form. In contrast, MECI corresponding to the -NH₃⁺ form involves energetically less accessible puckering of the coumarin ring and thus favors radiative deactivation of the S_1 excited state. This finding explains the increase of the experimentally observed quantum yields in the acidic environment.

A detailed Franck-Condon analysis (ESI) of the fluorescence spectral profiles [39–41] for all three compounds in the acidic and neutral pH revealed that at the neutral pH the excited state relaxation is dominated by a group of vibrational modes with the frequency ~ 1500 cm⁻¹. However, at low pH the relaxation likely involves two groups of high frequency vibrational modes; one at ~ 1500 cm⁻¹ and the second at ~ 1000 -1200 cm⁻¹. This is consistent with the results of the theoretical calculations, which indicate that there is a group of 3 vibrational modes around 1500 cm⁻¹ with a large non-adiabatic coupling (NAC) between the S_1 and S_0 states in the deprotonated system (Tables S3 and S4). Together with the above-mentioned large scale out-of-plane

movements of the amino group, these vibrational modes contribute to a fast S_1 - S_0 internal conversion, which successfully competes with the radiative (fluorescence) relaxation in the deprotonated, neutral form. The involvement of the additional set of vibrational modes at low pH can be attributed to electronic distortions induced by the protonation of the amino group. The protonation adds additional 3 vibrational modes at $\sim 1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$; namely a ring-breathing of the coumarin and julolidine part, as well as a higher group of oscillators coupling the C=O stretching with the coumarin breathing mode.

In our calculations we found that the intersystem crossing (ISC) [42] between the S_1 and T_2 states in both protonated and deprotonated form is relatively slow ($k_{ISC} \sim 10^6\text{ s}^{-1}$) and thus cannot effectively compete with the fluorescence ($k_F > 10^8\text{ s}^{-1}$) or much faster $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ internal conversion. The $S_1 \rightarrow T_2$ ISC followed by a vibrational relaxation within the triplet manifold to T_1 therefore does not contribute significantly to the non-radiative deactivation of the S_1 state. Absence of an apparent triplet-triplet absorption in the transient absorption spectra of both forms, measured by a nanosecond laser flash photolysis, supports this conclusion (Fig. S30).

To demonstrate their practical utility, we tested the compounds **1**, **2** and **3** as pH probes of yeast vacuoles in acidic conditions. Yeast cells pump the excess protons into the vacuole to maintain the neutral pH in the cytoplasm, whereby they significantly acidify the vacuole to the pH values below 5.5 [43–45]. As shown in Fig. 5, all three probes yielded excellent contrast in microscopic observation of the vacuoles of the living cells. The localization was confirmed by a commercial FM4-64 [46] red-fluorescent dye that selectively stains yeast vacuolar membranes (Fig. 5B, 5F, 5J). Due to their small size, high lipophilicity ($\log P > 1.9$; Table S5) and brightness, the probes developed here show rapid staining (observed within 3 min. compared to the 15–30 min. for the CMAC derivatives [33]) and thus require only short exposure times. Thanks to their high fluorescence quantum yields, an additional advantage of the novel coumarin fluorescent probes is the low required working concentration (1 μM compared to 100 μM of CMAC derivatives [33]). This allows us to observe cells for up to 2 hours without detectable toxic effects (data not shown). Our effort to circumvent the formation of the non-emissive TICT state thus resulted in an approximately 2-fold increase in the rate of staining even at 10-times lower probe concentration relative to the twisted dimethylamino analogue.

Fig. 5 Fluorescent microscope images of the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* strain BY4741 visualizing its vacuoles. Panels A, E, I show the vacuolar lumen stained with 1 μ M probe **1** (A), probe **2** (E) and probe **3** (I) with filter set (U-FCFP and U-FRFP Olympus). Panels B, F, J show vacuolar membranes stained for 60 min with the 10 μ M FM 4-64. The merged images (C, G, K; combination of A+B, E+F and I+J, respectively) show specific localization of probes in vacuoles. The staining was observed immediately after the probes were added under fluorescent microscope. Panels D, H, L show the same cell morphology monitored in a transmission mode. The scale bar corresponds to 2 μ m

3. Conclusion

In summary, we described the photochemistry and the sensing properties of three new 3-aminocoumarin fluorescent turn-on pH probes for strongly acidic conditions with rigidized julolidyl scaffold. We showed that a systematic methylation of the amino group can be used to effectively tune both the fluorescence enhancement factor as well as the usable pH range of the probes. Finally, we also showed that the developed probes can be used to effectively image the vacuolar lumen of the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* cells.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jakub Joniak: Investigation; Data curation **Henrieta Stankovičová:** Validation; Writing - review & editing **Šimon Budzák:** Conceptualization; Data curation; Investigation; Roles/Writing - original draft **Milan Sýkora:** Data curation; Investigation; Roles/Writing - original draft **Katarína Gaplovská-Kyselá:** Data curation; Investigation; Roles/Writing - original draft **Marek Cigáň:** Conceptualization; Visualization; Roles/Writing - original draft; Writing - review & editing

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Synthesis and characterization of cpds; details of photochemical and pH titration experiments; determination of photophysical parameters and sensing properties; details of the quantum-chemical calculations; Franck-Condon analysis of the emission profiles

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Figure captions

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Fig. 3 The CIE 1976 (u',v')-chromaticity diagram with marked yellowish-green fluorescence colour of studied coumarin pH probes and corresponding chromaticity coordinates u' and v' for each probe.

Fig. 4 Frontier molecular orbitals of the partially occupied S₁ state. The table below the images summarizes the vertical excitation energies calculated at various levels of theory using def2-TZVPP basis set and water as solvent. The CC2 gas phase excitation energies were corrected for solvent effects using LR CAM-B3LYP solvent shifts.

Fig. 5 Fluorescent microscope images of the yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* strain BY4741 visualizing its vacuoles. Panels A, E, I show the vacuolar lumen stained with 1 μM probe **1** (A), probe **2** (E) and probe **3** (I) with filter set (U-FCFP and U-FRFP Olympus). Panels B, F, J show vacuolar membranes stained for 60 min with the 10 μM FM 4-64. The merged images (C, G, K; combination of A+B, E+F and I+J, respectively) show specific localization of probes in vacuoles. The staining was observed immediately after the probes were added under fluorescent microscope. Panels D, H, L show the same cell morphology monitored in a transmission mode. The scale bar corresponds to 2 μm.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Table 1. Spectral characteristics and pK_a values of studied coumarin probes **1-3**.

Compound	λ_{abs} [nm]	λ_{em} [nm]	ε [dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹]	Φ	Bs [dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹]	pK_a
pH = 7.68 / pH = 1.90						
1	380/426	528/512	16600/11700	0.43/0.67	7100/7800	3.43
2	379/431	531/512	16800/7200	0.13/0.55	2500/4000	3.46
3	386/435	504/512	13200/17400	0.02/0.68	300/12000	4.23

λ_{abs} - UV-Vis absorption maximum, λ_{em} - emission (fluorescence) maximum, ε - molar absorption coefficient, Φ –

fluorescent quantum yield (accuracy: \pm 10-15 %), Bs – probe brightness ($\varepsilon \times \Phi$)